

COVERAGE OF AGRICULTURAL INNOVATIONS AND FOOD SECURITY BY SELECT NATIONAL DAILIES IN NIGERIA

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Keywords

Coverage, Agricultural Innovations, Food Security, National Dailies, Nigeria.

Abstract: *This study examined the coverage of agricultural innovations and food security by three Nigerian national dailies which were Vanguard, The Punch, and Daily Trust newspapers between January 1 and December 31, 2024. The objectives of the study were to investigate the frequency of reportage accorded the issue, assess the prominence given, and identify the major sources of stories, on these issues. One research hypothesis guided the study which was anchored on Agenda Setting and Development Media Theories. Using content analysis, the population of 1,098 editions of the newspapers was examined, from which 252 were sampled through purposive and composite (constructed) week techniques. Data were collected with coding sheet and analysed using frequency tables and simple percentages, and hypotheses tested with Chi-square Goodness of Fit. Findings revealed frequent reportage of agricultural innovations and food security by the three newspapers, with Daily Trust giving more focus to agricultural innovations. Findings also showed that the newspapers accorded high prominence to such stories under investigation. The study concluded that Nigerian national dailies are actively reporting on agricultural innovations and food security but however emphasised on the need for more in-depth and sustained reportage. It was recommended that Nigerian newspapers should accord much priority, in-depth reportage, and editorial focus to enhance awareness, inform readers on the issue and highlight possible solutions and policy implications that will help strengthen agricultural development and food security in Nigeria.*

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Introduction

The survival of businesses and modern societies is fundamentally rooted in communication, especially in places where democracy is merely evolving, highlighting the enormous role of access to credible information in the shaping of participation to national development. Considerably, the definition of the mass media underscores that they are channels carefully organised and designed in forms that enhance the dissemination of information, to large and varied audiences at the same time. Among other things, newspapers, radio, television and digital platforms are expressions of the mass media, and they all contribute to shaping the social, political and economic realities of citizens and the globe.

Recent scholarly contributions bring to the fore, the multifaceted functions of the media, albeit functioning as a non-neutral component of society. Researchers posit that the media vigorously direct public priorities, impact group judgment and govern the frames from which the public assess and analyse issues. The media, McQuail (2019) explains, is an influential social institution. They shape how the environment is understood and how their users encounter public life. In this role, they provide interpretation to events, apportion the kind of

value that issues receive, as well as cultivate shared responses to challenges. This function is particularly important in places where public awareness is critical to attracting participation; it thrives on the media's ability to choose, highlight and frame issues that mould citizens' considerations of important and worthy materials in society. Generally known as the agenda setting function, the media, in this role, act as a precursor to national development. They contribute to social wellbeing, and to this end, mass communication holds a relevance that cuts beyond sharing pieces of information; its scope extends to social guidance, public mobilisation and policy influence.

In Nigeria, where information flow is a leading occurrence for the government and development agencies, the media serve the role of a conduit between policy decisions and public awareness. Their ability to set agenda materialises in the attention given to national issues by members of the public through the visibility that they create. Thus, this function is central in diverse sectors including agriculture, particularly, given that the success of policies is dependent on access by the public, and its acceptance, which is generally expected to attract participation. Where the media pays attention influences where the attention of citizens tilts to, and what they consider urgent too and important. According to Valenzuela and

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McCombs (2020), persistent media consideration continually influences how prominent development issues feature in public discourse.

The majority, if not all of Nigerians, are affected by the turnout of events in the agriculture sector and food security. While some depend on the sector for employment, others work for income and household survival. Agricultural communication remains very important matters beyond editorial preference in the media; it is a marker for development responsibility. With consistent coverage of agricultural innovation and food security, citizens engage policies from an informed standpoint. In cases where coverage is weak, there is an insufficient public awareness. In turn, efforts aimed at development lose momentum. The realities of a nation with a vast population should receive a commensurate media attention to agriculture because survival is closely tied to food production and access.

The existence of the mass media is shaped by societal needs, which they, in turn, are accountable. The media's relevance in society rises and falls on their ability to fulfill the roles of information, education, and citizen mobilisation around shared concerns. Top on the list of expectations from the media in Nigeria, given its peculiarities as a developing nation, cut across corrective and developmental

functions. In light of this, scholars in some quarters consider the role of the media to include public education, considerably in societies with unequal and unequitable distribution of education systems. According to McQuail (2019) media houses serve as agents of social continuity through their interpretation of their environment, helping individuals make sense of the environment where they live or work.

The reality in Nigeria, however, is that the news agenda is predominantly yielded to political competition, conflict narratives and elite centred debates dominate news agendas. Issues concerning development are mostly featured in moments of crises, policy launches or controversies. An observation by the UNESCO (2021) indicates that for communication processes designed for development to be effective, there has to be consistency, explanation and context beyond one-off coverage that highlight curated events. Contrariwise, agriculture spreads progressively through revolution, variation and behavioural change. The failure of the media to meet these needs makes public engagement grow weak and development goals suffer. Particularly, newspapers with national spread can turn around this reality by deliberately covering issues that reflect social realities.

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However, McQuail (2019) notes that newspapers retain a fundamental place in the agenda formation discourse. The author avers that this suffices from their interpretive strength. Newspapers with a national spread including Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust influence elite discourse and policy conversations despite the rise of digital platforms, as they provide reference for policymakers, academics and civil society organisations.

Agriculture can be defined as the science, art, and practice of cultivating soil, growing crops, and raising animals for food, fiber, and other products used to sustain and enhance human life. This multifaceted discipline encompasses a range of activities, including but not limited to soil cultivation, crop production, livestock management, horticulture, agroforestry, and the production of food and non-food products through various farming systems. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (2021), The United Nations defines agriculture as consisting of all activities associated with the cultivation of plants and livestock for human use and includes a range of economic activities and practices designed to improve food security, foster rural development, and promote sustainable land use and practices (United Nations, 2022).

For agriculture, its processes and policy frameworks are scientific in nature. This hinders its reportage in sensational manners. In spite of this reality, editorial processes frequently put a ceremonial lid on agricultural stories, confined within the context of government activities. The truism about this finds credence in the submission of Ojebuyi and Salawu (2019), who submit that newspapers that operate in Nigeria yield substantial privilege to political realities and conflict over development reporting, an imbalance that impinges on the framing and valuing of agriculture, ultimately shaping public awareness and policy responsiveness.

The sector, however, is reputed for preponderant issue that imperils productivity and sustainability. Similarly, the Food and Agriculture Organisation (2023) explains the relationship between low productivity and post-harvest losses, a development believed to be addressable through the guided adoption of novel processes that improve efficiency, resilience and output.

Meanwhile, innovation in agriculture culminates from the combination of novel ideas, as well as practices and technologies that are objectively positioned to improve performance across the value chain. These innovations are believed to yield occasions for improved food availability and farmer income.

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Agricultural innovation involves the practices, systems and technologies that are required for boosting productivity, enhanced sustainability and adapt to climate change, through new development in areas such as precision agriculture, data analysis and robotics. Furthermore, it involves agricultural production techniques through the use of new machineries crop management strategies and new irrigation methods, improved agricultural products, new crop varieties, nutritious foods, innovative food processing methods, better storage, and other development in the food chain (Food and Agricultural Organisation, 2019). A few examples include developing drought-tolerant crops, smart agriculture, vertical farming, precise irrigation, and the use of ecologically friendly fertilizers and herbicides. It also entails creating new value chains, markets, and business models to support agriculture's economic sustainability and competitiveness in order to meet consumer expectations for organic or sustainably produced food (Oladejo & Ogunniyi, 2019).

Communication, notwithstanding, has an important role in the achievement of a set impact for which agricultural innovations are adopted. Poorly communicated innovations suffer resistance, misinterpretation or neglect. Food and Agricultural Organisation (2021) emphasises, and rightly so, that effective

agricultural innovation systems depend on information flow among researchers, policymakers and farmers. Media coverage, therefore, stands as one of the single most important aspect of agricultural development. The consistent highlight of successful adoption in newspaper nips scepticism in the bud; it rather encourages participation. Edegoh and Asemah (2020) argue that scarce media attention to agricultural technology manifests in scanty public knowledge, which ultimately translates to sluggish adoption rates. National newspapers thus function as intermediaries between innovation developers and society.

Food security is a resultant effect of having food surplus, food safety, food quality, food accessibility, and food affordability in the system. However, a hungry citizen who has little or no access to quality and safe foods will appreciate anything that is edible-like, that is presented to him as food without minding the quality, neatness, and the composition. Ones he perceived it, he feels free enough to take it in to satisfy his hunger. Food therefore is defined as any edible or consumable material present that could be taken to satisfy human hunger and gain energy to do work (Nwadike, Ekwebelam, Anyanwu, Obele & Onyejelem, 2023). Food then is considered as a necessary and basic need of every human as it is expected to work and have response in all the above mentioned attributes

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to the body of the consumer (Nwadike, et al. 2023).

Meanwhile, food security represents a pressing development challenge in Nigeria. It speaks to a mass access to adequate, harmless and healthy food vital for a vigorous life. Worsening food insecurity that characterises the recent time has been attributed to conflict, climate stress and economic instability. This assertion is backed by reports by the Global Hunger Index, which ranked Nigeria among countries facing debilitating hunger challenges (Global Hunger Index, 2023). Markers of these challenges range from rising food prices, to declining purchasing power and insecurity in farming communities. The result is that food security issues affect health, education and national stability. The role of media coverage is to shape both perception and prioritisation. UNESCO (2021), thus, advises a sustained media engagement in view of maintaining food security on the public agenda. Newspapers, as one of the important media, has the capacity to connect policy debates with household realities. Nonetheless, coverage is often sparse, wearying public pressure for long-term solutions.

In modern days, technological change is reported to have transformed agricultural practice across developing economies, including Nigeria. Nigeria's Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development (2021)

particularly note that adoption is very to agricultural transformation. However, while these gains remain, adoption is unequal and largely attributed to awareness gaps and trust issues. Yet, studies congruently reveal positive relationship between media reportage and public acceptance of innovations. Public acceptance, therefore, continue to dwindle over concerns of health, environmental safety and seed control.

This study, thus, set out to assess national newspapers' coverage of agricultural innovation and food security issues in Nigeria. The study charts a course towards understanding how the mainstream media responds to issues related to agriculture in the nation. Its investigation focuses on determining the extent and nature of coverage. Also, the study examines frequency, prominence and sources. Its outcome is expected to show evidence for the performance of the media, print particularly, in covering and reporting this important development issue.

Statement of the Problem

Human survival and the development of nations have, for a long time, depended on the quality of agriculture, among other things. This is the case in developing nation, as it is the case in developed nations. Through agriculture, food is provided, in addition to jobs for citizens, revenue generation and social stability, thus occupying a critical and vital role in the

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sustenance of rural livelihoods. Nigeria is reputed for a large deposit of crude, yet agriculture remains a viable contributor across all indices of economic growth. Nevertheless, the sector is bedeviled by enormous challenges that impinge on food security and sustainable development. The attributes of these challenges are clear and are manifest in crude farming engagements, poorly functional machines, and climate variability, among many things.

Despite improved mechanisation and seed varieties, studies show an unappreciable adoption rate among farmers. Typically, addressing these challenges should be at the front burner through improved information flow, policy support and sustained public engagement. Dailies with national coverage are typically thought to have a distinct role in midwifing this process through their reporting. As Amannah, Onyebuchi, Obayi and Anorue (2017, p. 32) observe, “The media are expected to inform and educate society on development sectors such as agriculture as part of their surveillance responsibility”. Sequel to the foregoing, effective communication presages the adoption of innovation.

Reality, however, contrasts this expectation of the media in Nigeria, with ‘artificial’ reports of agricultural innovations in staccato forms in national newspapers. Studies reveal that reports occasionally occupy newspaper pages in crises

situations, and other managed events, with follow up treated as a fluke. The dominant issues revolve around politics, crime and security, with development issues such as agriculture, approached as a secondary concern. UNESCO (2011) notes that media attention to food security often peaks only when disasters are predicted or emergencies occur. This arrangement makes for a dilemma among farmers and other stakeholders who rely on the media for direction. Likewise, Okorie and Salawu (2017) and Ojebuyi and Edewor (2020) affirm that agricultural stories are poorly known, because they are not visible in the mainstream media.

In addition to the foregoing, Asogwa (2023) underscores recurrent worries concerning under reporting of agricultural programmes and food insecurity, which results in a widening gap between development efforts and supposed beneficiaries. While studies have established this groundwork, it is unknown how much devotion has been committed by national newspapers, in particular, to issues regarding agricultural innovations and food security. The gap, therefore, lies in the paucity of empirical submissions in this area; hence, this study investigates the subject matter by investigating the manifest content of select national dailies, namely Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust,

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to ascertain their contribution to this development objective.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to:

- i. investigate the frequency of reportage accorded to agricultural innovations and food security by Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers;
- ii. Examine the level of prominence given to agricultural innovations and food security by Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers;
- iii. Ascertain the major source of stories on agricultural innovations and food security by Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers;

Research Hypothesis

The research hypothesis for this study was formulated in the alternate as follows:

H₁: There is a significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovation and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers;

Literature Review

Newspaper

Newspapers are traditional print media publications that provide news, information, and analysis on diverse issues, including current events, politics, business, culture, and sports. Newspapers traditionally consist of multiple

sections, such as news, opinion/editorial, features, and classifieds, and are published daily or weekly to inform and educate readers about local, national, and international events.. Newspapers generally create the room for comprehensive reportage, investigative detailing, and elongated storytelling that could be impossible in other media formats.

Moreover, over the years, newspapers have experienced modifications owing to the permeation of fast-improving technologies. Nowadays, popular among readers are digital versions of newspapers, as they make for quick accessing of news stories and other related materials. These newspapers are designed in a manner that provides multimedia, interactive and real-time content. In turn, readers enjoy convenience and personalisation in their search for news content.

In Nigeria, printed newspapers have maintained their position as a keystone of the nation's media topography, and they provide news, engender public discussion, and information interchange. In the face of online news displays, traditional newspapers endure as a noteworthy shaper of public discourse, keeping citizens abreast of goings-on, and sustaining journalistic standards in the nation. A never-to-miss feature of traditional papers in Nigeria is the continued trust it receives, following the belief among many readers that they maintain journalism

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ethics and editorial oversight (Olorunleke, 2017). Although Olorunleke's position yields to contestation, it is noteworthy that printed newspapers are reputed for detailed reportage that stems from thoroughly fact-checked and rigorous processes that uphold objectivity, balance and accuracy.

Nonetheless, traditional newspapers are faced with diverse inhibitions that manifest in low circulation of newspapers, which translates to, among other things, dwindling revenue, and tense rivalry with digital media platforms (John, 2019).

Agricultural Communication

Agricultural communication comprises the dissemination of facts arising from activities of farming to agriculture stakeholders. Its aim is to enhance the profitability of farming and farmers. Akande and Fab-Usoro (2016) underscore that agricultural communication, when accessible to farmers, keeps them informed and helps them make decisions that are rooted in factual data and information designed with specific objectives that improve the farming systems.

This aspect of communication is aimed at engendering a positive influence on the disposition of farmers. The view is that they are aligned with global standards of agricultural engagements (Daudu & Balogun, 2014). The introduction of new technologies is critical to

the achievement of these goals among farmers. It serves two roles, which include the provision of fundamental facts that arm farmers with required skills that improve farming practices. Effective change requires not only the transfer of information but also practical training in implementing new technologies (Amaza & Oyawa, 2017).

In addition, agricultural communication simplifies the interchange of information. The phenomenon also contributes to informed decision-making, encouraging collaboration among agricultural stakeholders.

Agricultural Reporting

Agricultural reporting consists of gathering and presentation of news on agriculture to an audience through a mass medium. Agricultural news refers to events, developments, observations in the agricultural sector (or outside the sector but have direct or indirect implications to agriculture), which are of interest to the audience of a specific medium. This includes news about outbreak of disease in a farm, new farming techniques, policies on agriculture, agro-business news, agric-related food security issues, agric-related environment issues, breakthroughs in genetic engineering. Development in the various form of farming such as crop, pig, sheep, fish, organic and inorganic farming. Coverage of issues, events or occurrences in these and other related areas is

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what agricultural reporting entails (Nwabueze, 2015).

All forms of reporting straight news, features, interpretative, investigative etc which are used to keep the audience abreast of developments in agriculture constitute agricultural reporting. While the political correspondent is asking a politician to explain what a recent government policy holds for the citizenry, the agricultural reporter is asking the same politician to explain the implications of the policy on the agric sector (Nwabueze, 2015).

Knowledge and information are important factors for accelerating agricultural development by increasing agricultural production and improving marketing and distribution (Arokoyo, 2011, cited in Haruna, 2013, p.120).

Agricultural Innovations

By definition, agricultural innovation refers to the processes by which individuals and organisations improve upon existing products, processes and systems in such manner that they serve better social and economic use, (Tropical Agriculture Platform, 2016) cited in Ren, Alexander and Andrea (2019). Agricultural innovation involves the practices, systems and technologies that are required for boosting productivity, enhanced sustainability and adapt to climate change, through new development in areas such as precision agriculture, data

analysis and robotics. Furthermore, it involves agricultural production techniques through the use of new machineries crop management strategies and new irrigation methods, improved agricultural products, new crop varieties, nutritious foods, innovative food processing methods, better storage, and other development in the food chain (Food and Agricultural Organisation, 2019).

The concept points to the provision and adoption of improved techniques, apparatuses, and resources aimed at increasing productivity, efficiency, profitability, and sustainability in agricultural processes. Modern farming integrates cutting-edge technologies like robots, biotechnology, precision agriculture, and big data analytics to solve problems and seize opportunities (Lwoga, 2010). Instances comprise the development of drought-tolerant crops, among other things that also contribute to the protection of natural resources. It comprises the creation of modified value chains, marketplaces, and business processes that aid economic progression through agricultural activities that provide the expectations of consumers (Oladejo & Ogunniyi, 2019).

Moreover, the introduction of new technologies and methods contribute to how stakeholders deal with problems that challenge proper agricultural processes. In view of providing solutions that meet the agricultural needs of a

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nation, cooperation must subsist among farmers, researchers, government agencies, and private businesses (Alabi & Oyedeji, 2016). Innovations, in the context of agriculture, follows several details that involve the creation, implementation and dissemination of novel technologies and knowledge, comprising education, among other things.

Agricultural innovation contributes to the production of food. This and other improvements that are obtained through innovations are reinforced by data. Olumide, Fakoya, Adeyemo and Olorunsola (2017) show that the uptake of improved variations of maize in sub-Saharan Africa yielded notable improvements, which in turn manifested in food output and farmer earnings.

Food Security

Food security is a resultant effect of having food surplus, food safety, food quality, food accessibility, and food affordability in the system. However, a hungry citizen who has little or no access to quality and safe foods will appreciate anything that is edible-like, that is presented to him as food without minding the quality, neatness, and the composition. Once he perceived it, he feels free enough to take it in to satisfy his hunger. Food therefore is defined as any edible or consumable material present that could be taken to satisfy human hunger and

gain energy to do work (Nwadike, Ekwebelam, Anyanwu, Obele & Onyejelem, 2023).

Also, food security is a situation that exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preference for an active and healthy life ((Food and Agricultural Organisation, 2022).

Theoretical Framework

Agenda Setting Theory

Agenda setting theory describes the relationship between media contents and its effect on individual and society at large. According to Asemah (2011) it explains the ability of the media to influence the salience of topic of the public agenda. Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw propounded the theory in 1972/1973. The propositions of the theory are:

- i. The media, especially the print form, reflect a different social truth, they filter, choose and shape it; the better an issue is given coverage, the more likely it is perceived more important than others;
- ii. People get their news from limited sources because people do not pay attention to all outlets;

Agenda setting theory further explain the observation of Walter Lippman on public opinion that the media act as a bridge between 'the world outside and the pictures on our head'

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(Akakwandu, 2020). However, according to Folarin cited in Anni, Nyekwuere, Nwanguma and Ugwuanyi (2017), agenda setting suggest a predetermined disposition of issues in the media, which translates to what the public considers important at a given time.

Critics however argue that the agenda setting theory assumes that the mass media audience is passive and merely abusing the issues presented to them by the media. Whereas, in real situations, the audience may actively lookout for information that align with their interest or just ignore the agenda set by the media. It is believed that the media, rather than set agenda, only mirror the society. They do not create events. They only report event that are taking place in the environment which it operates.

But, there is a psychological and scientific merit of the theory. Here, the frequency to which an issue is publicized in the media, the more such an issue becomes very well stored in the mind of the individual. And, the more the individual perceive it as being important and think about it, the more he/she can recall. The media here provide the cues to judge the importance of an issue from their salience and to focus more on them.

It is a fact that the media may not always determine what we think but can highlight on what we think about. Hence, Agenda setting theory seem quite appropriate to help us

understand the pervasive role of the media in the society (Ogbuoshi, 2020). The relevance of agenda setting theory to the study on newspapers coverage of agricultural innovations and food security lies in its ability to explain how the media influences public perceptions and priorities regarding agricultural innovations and food security, especially in Nigeria.

The Development Media Theory

The development media theory was propounded by Dennis McQuail in 1987. The theory owes its origin to the UNESCO's MacBride Commission set up in 1979. The theory is rooted on the need of the developing nations to use the media for accelerated development, accepts national development as its overriding objectives. This essentially implies that the press must be placed as a tool on the path of a country's economic development (Ogbuoshi, 2020).

The theory is peculiar to developing countries because they are the ones that need to achieve the goals of development. Development media theory came as result of the limitations of the traditional Western models of the media, which give priority to the free flow of information and individualistic values. One basic fundamental tenets of the theory among others according to McQuail (1987) cited in Asemah (2011) is that, the media should accept and carry out positive development tasks in line with nationally established policy. This however explains the

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fact that the development media theory can serve as a lens to help analyse how national newspapers in Nigeria cover the various innovations in agriculture in the country and how they contribute to national development efforts.

The national newspapers can use their medium to inform and educate the public on certain technological advancements, scientific breakthrough and even the benefits of adopting such innovations. This theory is very relevant to this study in the sense that it provides a framework to understanding how the media can support national development efforts, the theory also helps to explain how the media can focus on promoting innovation, fostering understanding among stakeholders, help to support government initiatives and equally engender a balance and inclusive reportage.

Review of Related Studies

The following related studies were reviewed to support this study as follows:

Agboola, O., Abdulfatai, B, Khadijat, A. O. & Abiola, A. (2015). Press Coverage of Food Security in Nigeria: A Case of the Guardian Newspaper. Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development 6 (4), 219-228, retrieved from <https://www.iiste.org>

The main objectives of this study was to examine the reportage of food security as it

affects Nigeria, and asses how far the Nigerian mass media accords reportorial relevance to the issue, which is closely linked to the very first of the MDGs that the United Nations floated in the turn of the current century. Therefore, the study focused on food security in Nigeria using the lens of the mass media. The study purposely selected six month editions of The Guardian newspaper, which was content analysed using prominence, variety and directions as content categories. The study used a 132-day sample size out of six months from the week days only. Findings of this study revealed that The Guardian newspaper demonstrated gross indifference to an issue of global critical importance like food security. The study recommended that both The Guardian and the Nigerian government should pay attention to the problem. Therefore, the above study relates to the one at hand in the sense that the both studies employed content analysis research method. Second, both studies sought to underscore food security and press coverage of the issue in Nigeria.

Awojobi, E.A. & Adeokun, O.A., (2012). Content Analysis of Agricultural Issues Reported in Two Nigerian Daily Newspapers. Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal). 800 retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/800>

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This research seeks to use two popular newspapers (Punch and Guardian) for daily newspapers based on their current involvement in dissemination of agricultural information. Samples of the newspapers between 2007 and 2010 were analysed for daily reportage, space allocation and types of stories published. All data collected was analysed with the application of simple descriptive statistics. Findings demonstrated that 70%, 78.8%, 66.3% and 60% of analysed newspapers did not report any agricultural issues in years 2007, 2008, 2009 and 2010 respectively. Findings revealed that reported agricultural issues, majority reported 1-2 stories per day. Judging by past and present trends, the authors concluded that newspapers are not likely to make significant contribution to dissemination of agricultural information for enhanced agricultural production.

Therefore, the study relates to the current study in the knowledge that both sought to investigate a content analysis of technology and innovation in the Nigerian newspapers such as The Punch, Vanguard and The Guardian newspapers. Also, both studies adopted content analysis as the basic research design.

Research Methodology

This study adopted content analysis as a research design. It was used to examine the reportage of agricultural innovations and food security issues in the Punch, Vanguard and

Daily Trust newspapers. Content analysis was adopted because it is a research design that involves an objective and systematic analysis or study of the content of documents that are manifest (Nwodu, 2017). In other words, what is to be content analysed is only what is visible to the eye (Ubah & Iwok, 2021).

In view of these, the researcher was convinced that content analysis research design was more appropriate for analysis of the coverage accorded to agricultural innovations and food security issues by the Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers in Nigeria from January 1st, 2024 to December 31st, 2024.

The population of this study comprised 1,098 copies (editions) of the selected newspapers published between January 1st 2024, to December 31st 2024, (a period of twelve (12) months). Within this period, each of the selected national dailies published a total of 366 editions, including weekend editions. The selected newspapers were not the only newspapers in Nigeria as at the time of the study but the researcher purposively selected them based on the fact that they have wide national coverage, editorial independence, large circulation strength, national acceptability, wide readership, influence of reputation and credibility, and availability of archive (both hard and online copies). The papers also are tabloid in size and published from Monday to Sunday.

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The newspapers occasionally cover agricultural innovation and food security issues. Even though this may not be their primary focus, it is not however certain whether or not they do this more frequently.

The sample size for this study was 252 (two hundred and fifty-two) issues (editions) selected from a total of 1,098 (one thousand and ninety eight) issues (editions) of the three selected newspapers (The Punch, Vanguard and Daily Trust). The sample size represented 23% of the population. Here, the researcher decided to study that percentage of the entire population rather than the whole population, and the justification was for some practical reasons which include balancing the constraints of resources, feasibility, generalisability, efficiency and to also allow for effective statistical analysis and the validity of findings.

A multi-stage sampling technique was used for this study. First, the researcher adopted purposive sampling technique in selecting the three (3) newspapers for this study (based on the reasons stated above). This technique allowed the researcher to deliberately select what constitute the sample for the study based on certain predetermined conditions or objectives which this study intends to achieve. Second, the composite (constructed) week/month sampling technique developed by Riffe, Aust and Lacy (1993) cited in Wimmer

and Dominick (2011), was adopted to select the newspaper editions from January 1st to December, 31st, 2024 across the three selected national dailies (Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust) which gave resulted in 252 (two hundred and fifty- two) editions of the newspapers. The choice of this sampling technique was due to its proven effectiveness in ensuring more representation in media content analysis carried out over a longer period of time. And, also to avoid the pitfalls that may arise from using the continuous week technique (Jammy, Luke & Stella, 2023). This limitations include: poor representativeness, susceptibility to event-driven bias, inability to control for (day-of-the-week) cyclical variations and low reliability for longitudinal studies (Hester & Dougall, 2007); Neuendorf (2002) and Riff, Lacy, Fico, (2005) and Song & Chang (2011). According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011, p.163) cited in Amannah, Onyebuchi, Obayi and Anorue (2017, p.262), “a composite week/months sampling technique was superior to both random sample and consecutive day sample techniques when dealing with newspaper contents”.

However, the researcher first stratified the twelve (12) months periods into months (January 1st to December 31st, 2024). And from each month, one constructed week was generated and this was done by randomly

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selecting one week day from any week in the month. However, the process continued in all the days of the week until they were fully represented. This resulted to seven (7) sampled editions per months for each newspaper. Here, seven (7) editions x 12 months = 84 editions for each newspaper. This period multiply by three newspapers yielded 36 weeks or 252 days (Total editions of the newspapers)

The inter-coder reliability test was used to access the degree to which the coders agreed. To ascertain this, Holsti Index Formula (1969) cited in Wimmer and Dominick (2017), was adopted to calculate the inter-coder reliability test and the two coders independently analysed a random sample of 10% of the contents. The formula is shown below:

$$CR = \frac{2M}{N1 + N2}$$

Where:

M = Number of items agreed upon

N1= Number of items for Coder 1

N2 = Number of items for coder 2

CR = Co-efficient of Reliability

Therefore,

$$CR = \frac{2(104)}{124 + 124}$$

$$CR = \frac{208}{248} = 0.838$$

The result of the correlation coefficient of the relation as calculated in the test of reliability of the coders showed that the average percentage

of agreement among the coders was 0.84%, which is considered acceptable for quantitative content analysis.

However, the unit of analysis for this study includes: news stories (straight), features stories and articles, opinions, columns, editorials, advertorials, comments, interviews and pictures that carries issues that relates to agricultural innovations and food security issues published in the selected newspapers in Nigeria during the period of this study.

The following content categories were formulated to help analyse the contents and also serve as an instruments for solving the problem under investigation. These include: Sustainable Farming Practices, Climate-Smart Agriculture, Post-Harvest Innovations, Biotechnology and Genetically Modified (GM) Crops, Precision Agriculture Technologies, Food Scarcity and Hunger, Access to Food, Government and International Food Initiatives/policies, Health and Nutrition,

The coding sheet was the main instrument for data collection in this study and it was used to code data pertaining to the newspapers coverage of agricultural innovation and food security issues in line with the unit of analysis and the coding parameters formulated by the researcher

Data for this study was recorded on the sheets having gone through pilot coding. The analysis

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of data from the coding exercise was arranged in tabular format. The format makes presentations clear and calculations of percentage scores feasible and chi-square goodness of fit statistical tool was used to test the hypothesis.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This segment of the study shows the breakdown of the analysis in relation to newspaper report on agricultural innovations and food security in

Nigeria from January 1st to December, 31st 2024. A total of 166 stories on agricultural innovations and food security issues were obtained from the sample size of 252 editions selected out of the 1,098 editions (total population) of the newspapers studied from the selected national dailies (Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers)

Table 1 Frequency of reportage accorded to agricultural innovations and food security issues by vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers

Newspapers	Total of Agric innovation stories		Total of Food security stories		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Vanguard	17	10	18	11	35	21
Punch	25	15	39	24	64	39
Daily Trust	58	35	9	5	67	40
Total	100	60	66	40	166	100

Data from the table 1 above shows that Daily Trust had the highest number of reports, 58 (35%) on agricultural innovations and the lowest of 9 (5%) on food security issues. The Punch had the highest reports of 39 (24%) on food security and only 25(15%) on agricultural innovation issues. Meanwhile, Vanguard had

the lowest reports of 17(10%) on agricultural innovations and 18(11%) on food security. However, the table shows that the three newspapers gave the highest reports of 60% stories on agricultural innovation and 40% of the stories on food security.

Table 2 the level of prominence given to agricultural innovations and food security issues by Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers

Prominence	Vanguard Newspaper		The Punch Newspaper		Daily Trust Newspaper		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%

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Front page	2	1	4	2.4	4	2	10	5.4
Inside Page	27	16	56	34	60	36	143	86
Back Page	6	4	4	2.4	3	2	13	8.4
Total	35	2	64	9	67	40	166	100

Table 2 indicates the degree of importance or the level of prominence accorded to agricultural innovations and food security reports by the selected national dailies through the pages of appearance of such stories. As shown in the data above, the three national dailies had majority of

their agricultural innovations and food security reports published in their inside pages. Daily Trust had the highest percentage with 40%, while Punch had about 39% and Vanguard had 21% (these percentages were rated based on their total frequency).

Table 3 Major sources of stories on agricultural innovations and food security issues by Vanguard, The Punch and the Daily Trust newspapers

Sources of Story	Vanguard Newspaper		The Punch Newspaper		Daily Trust Newspaper		Total	
	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%	Freq.	%
Government sources	23	14	40	24	47	28	110	66
Industry experts/scientist	3	2	10	6	8	5	21	13
International org./Agencies	4	2	8	5	10	6	22	13
Business/private sector	5	3	6	4	2	1	13	8
Farmer perspectives	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Total	35	21	64	39	67	40	166	100

Table 3 shows the major source(s) of stories on agricultural innovations and food security issues by the select national dailies in Nigeria. From the data presented, it is shown that Daily Trust had the highest source from government sources which is represented by 40%; Punch

had 39% and Vanguard had 21%. Again, the above table shows that Daily Trust had the highest source from international organization/agencies. This represented 6% (this percentage is stemmed from the frequency).

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Test of Hypotheses

One (1) hypothesis was tested in this study. The hypothesis tested whether there is a significant difference in the frequency of coverage of agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers.

Table 4 Chi-Square analysis of whether there is no significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers

Newspapers	Observed Frequency (O_i)	Expected Frequency (E_i)	X^2 . Cal. Value	X^2 3, 0.05 Critical Value
Vanguard	35	55	11	7.815
Punch	64			
Daily Trust	67			
Total	166			

The hypothesis tested in this study aimed to determine if there is a significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers. The null hypothesis (H_0) states that there is no significant difference. To test this hypothesis, the Chi-Square analysis was conducted comparing the observed frequency with the expected frequency across the three select national dailies on the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues. The result of the analysis above (Table 4) revealed that the calculated (x^2)

H_{01} : There is no significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers.

Table 1 addresses the hypothesis above. That is, it explains whether the null hypothesis stated above should be rejected or upheld.

value of 11 was far greater than the critical value of 7.815 at 3° of 0.05 alpha level. Therefore, the results suggest there was statistically significant differences in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers. Hence, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected. This result implies that the select national dailies did not accord equal attention to this development related issues which however is a reflection of the variations in news values, audience orientations and editorial policies of the newspapers. This variation by the Punch and

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Vanguard newspapers can be attributed to their urban editorial orientation, limited emphasises on development communication, inadequate rural news networks, low audience-driven content strategies and even the case of commercial pressures and sponsorships. These factors may have redirected their attention to coverage of politics, crime and other issues and giving limited attention to reportage of agricultural innovations and food security.

Discussion of Findings

In this section, the findings that emanate from the results in the data analysed and discussed as they provide answers to the research questions and research hypotheses formulated to guide the study.

Research Question One: What was the frequency of reportage accorded to agricultural innovations and food security between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers?

The answer to the above research question is found in Table 1 which shows the frequency of coverage on agricultural innovations and food security issues between the Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers. Data presented in Table 1 shows that Daily Trust newspapers' content was predominantly news-oriented, with a total of 67 news stories (that is, 58 news stories on agricultural innovations and 9 stories on food security issues).

Similarly, The Punch allocated 64 (25 stories on agricultural innovation and 39 on food security issues), indicating a more diversified editorial strategy. Meanwhile, Vanguard newspaper had a limited publication of 35 (17 stories on agricultural innovations and 18 on food security issues). Supporting the findings, Amannah, Onyebuchi, Obanyi and Anorue (2016, p.213), note that, "the media pay attention to information that is mind blowing or human interest oriented. Even though the media may decide to report agricultural activities of farmers or government actions towards boosting agriculture, the frame of presentation may show significant difference from other news events". However, the findings here revealed that the three national dailies gave a total of 100(60%) stories on agricultural innovation and 66 (40%) of the stories on food security.

From the findings above the dominance by the Daily Trust can be attributed to several interrelated factors which include the newspaper editorial orientation and audience focus (that is, its strong readership in Northern Nigeria where agriculture is the dominant economic activities). Also, Daily Trust tends to prioritise development-oriented reporting, mostly as it concern farming innovations, food security and rural development. This is in-line with the principles of development journalism, which place emphasis on the role of the media

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in promoting socio-economic development. Equally, a seasonal farming cycles and the diverse nature of agricultural activities in Nigeria also may have influence the patterns of coverage. These activities however generate more news contents for the newspaper.

Supporting the findings, the hypotheses test on whether there is a significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers, the computed Chi-Square(χ^2) test presented in table 4 shows the χ^2 critical value of 11 and the calculated critical value of 7.815 at 3° of 0.05 alpha level. This therefore indicates that there was significant difference in the frequency of coverage accorded agricultural innovations and food security issues between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers. Thus, the null hypotheses (H_0) was rejected, while the alternate (H_1) was upheld.

The theoretical implications of these findings align with agenda-setting theory, which suggests that the media's agenda influences public awareness and, consequently, the policy agenda. Here, the differences in coverage shows that the audiences of newspapers with higher frequency of coverage are likely to perceive agricultural innovations and food security issues as being an important national concern and whereas,

readers of national dailies with lower coverage may accord very less significance to the issues.

Research Question Two: What is the level of prominence given to agricultural innovations and food security between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers?

As shown in the data above (Table 2), the three national dailies studied had majority of their stories of agricultural innovations and food security reports published in their inside pages. Daily Trust had the highest percentage with 67 (40%), while Punch had 64(39%) and Vanguard had 35(21%) (These percentages are rated based on their total frequency). Moreover, the front pages of the newspapers had abysmal 10(5.4%) news stories and back pages 13(8.4%) for the three national dailies on coverage of agricultural innovations and food security issues compared to inside page. This implies that the three selected newspapers had significant differences on the level of prominence given to stories on agricultural innovations and food security issues. It is believed that national dailies that accorded greater prominence to agricultural innovations and food security issues are more likely to attract readers' attentions to this issues

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and thereby increasing public knowledge, encourage discourse and help to stimulate policy engagement.

It should be noted that the media have an obligation to cover agricultural innovations and food security, rather, journalists often ignore the agricultural initiative, innovations and food security and rather focus more on politics, crime and security stories. It is a fact that front page, center spread and back pages of newspapers are meant to attract attention and command prominence.

This finding however agrees with the assertion of Emeafor, Emeafor and Odionye (2017) that, most times newspapers use placement to show the importance attached to news stories, hence, the more a news story appears in the front page of a newspaper the priority it has over others. This also, agrees with the position of Amannah, Onyebuchi, Obayi and Anorue (2017, p.266) that, “the media through the placement of news stories, cause some stories to have a better attention and importance over others. This is the basic idea behind the Agenda Setting theory. The media, invariably, helps society to apportion priority to issues by making them prominent (a priority)”.

It should be noted that newspapers that provided front page placement, larger headlines, pictures, and detail report on agricultural innovations and food security

effectively increase the perceived importance of the issue and whereas, the ones that provided less visible coverage help to reduce their perceived urgency among the readers.

The above findings equally align with the principles of development media theory which emphasises on the role of the media in supporting national development goals mostly in developing countries. Agricultural innovations and food security occupies an important position in a nation's national development plan and the disparity in prominence on the reportage of the issue clearly shows the diverse level of commitment of the select national dailies to their ethical obligation.

Research Question Three: What was the major source of stories on agricultural innovations and food security between Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers?

Data on Table 3 shows that Daily Trust had the highest source from government sources. This is represented with 47 (28%), The Punch had 40(24%) stories from government sources. Meanwhile, Vanguard had the lowest of 23(14%) stories from government sources. These give the total of 110 (66%) stories from government sources across the three newspapers as shown on the table. However, no story was sourced from farmers' perspectives across the three newspapers as shown in the Table 3. The result

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of this shows that government source was the major source of stories on agricultural innovations and food security issues reported by the selected national dailies. The study also revealed that no story was sourced from farmers' perspectives.

The implication of this findings relate to the credibility and quality of information disseminated to the audience. It should be noted that newspapers that rely mostly on governments or official sources may present policy driven or government (institutional) perspective which may only emphasis achievement and policy interventions without giving proper representation to realities at the grassroots. On the other hand, national dailies that involve diverse sources such as farmers, scientist and researchers, stakeholders and development partners are likely to give out balance, context driven and comprehensive reporting. The differences in such utilisation can shape public understanding of agricultural innovations and food security issues in many ways and to a large extent influence public trust and policy discourse.

It is a fact therefore that agriculture and food security is fast becoming information sensitive and with that, getting access to information, especially from the government has become a necessity and a major resource for agricultural development and food security. National dailies,

as major sources of information, have the potential to influence public awareness, government policies, and the adoption of new agricultural innovations and food security. According to Awojibi and Adeokun (2012), the success in enhancing food production, providing income and job opportunities and ensure that the agricultural sub-sector performs its manifest functions in furtherance of rural and overall national development, depends largely on the communication system adopted to implement various agricultural programmes.

Conclusion

From the analysis made, materials reviewed and the findings of this study, it can be safely inferred that newspaper coverage of agricultural innovation and food security in Nigeria, is still very far from what is to be desired, this in terms of the frequency, prominence and news sources, accorded the general reportage of the issue by the media. This generally has serious implication on the salience of issue which relates to the subject matter under study. However, this is not unconnected to the fact that findings from this study revealed that there were significant differences in the level of prominence, frequency and major sources, given to the coverage of agricultural innovation and food security issues between Vanguard, Punch and Daily Trust newspapers, during the period under study.

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Considering the findings of this study, the Vanguard, The Punch and Daily Trust newspapers, showed reasonable efforts in their coverage of these issues by giving a reasonable frequent coverage, providing diversity in perspectives, giving prominence to the stories and even reports more on agricultural innovations issues than food security issues. The study revealed that government and international and food initiatives serve as the major sources of news with the objectives to help create a sustainable food chain in Nigeria.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

i. The Nigerian media especially newspaper organizations should float an agro-allied desk charged with the reportage of agricultural and allied issues in the country.

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ii. Nigerian newspapers should give due prominence to the coverage of agricultural innovations and food security issues. Greater percentage of stories on this issue should be allocated to front pages of the newspapers to help draw attention of readers, government and other stakeholders.

iii. Also, Nigerian newspapers should seek out the diverse range of farmer's perspectives on agricultural innovations and food insecurity in some marginalized communities and investigate their inabilities to utilise this emerging agricultural innovations and expertise.

iv. Newspapers in Nigeria should utilize more of other genres of journalistic writings (such as feature articles, editorial, columns, investigative/interpretative stories,) aside straight news reportage on the coverage of agricultural innovation and food security.

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